

MACHINE LEARNING MODEL FOR PREDICTING CUSTOMER CHURN IN SUBSCRIPTION BASED BUSINESS

Anusha Musunuri

University of Texas at Dallas, USA

ABSTRACT

Machine Learning Model for Predicting Customer Churn in Subscription-Based Businesses, the main goal of which is to predict which of your customers are likely to get churned from subscription services. As the number of subscription-based companies has grown in the last few years, so too have efforts to accurately predict and stop customer churn both because these methods mean sustaining a health rate and pipeline growth and using sophisticated algorithms to scan big customer databases for patterns of behaviors that precede stopping using the service from previous customers. It includes shopping behavior, payment history, and customer demographics. By training on new data, the model can make predictions to pinpoint which customers are likely churners, allowing businesses to intercept and retain those that have made a decision. These involve specific marketing actions as well as renewed retention offers. Companies can use The Machine Learning Model for Predicting Customer Churn in Subscription-Based Businesses to slash customer churn rates, boost overall loyalty, and earn more profits. This is an indispensable service for every subscription-driven business that wants to improve customer retention and stay ahead of the competition.

Keywords: Machine Learning, Subscription, Customer Data, Demographics, Proactive Measures

Cite this Article: Anusha Musunuri. (2024). Machine Learning Model for Predicting Customer Churn in Subscription Based Business. International Journal of Artificial Intelligence & Machine Learning, 3(2), 211–220.

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJAIML/VOLUME_3_ISSUE_2/IJAIML_03_02_017.pdf

I. INTRODUCTION

Customer churn refers to the loss of customers from a business or organization. In subscription-based businesses, customer churn is a critical metric measuring the rate at which customers cancel their subscriptions [1]. Predicting customer churn in subscription-based businesses is essential for businesses to identify and address potential issues that may lead to the loss of customers. It allows businesses to retain customers and, ultimately, increase revenue proactively [2].

The prediction of customer churn in subscription-based businesses involves the use of various data analysis techniques and models [3]. These techniques and models are used to identify patterns and trends in customer behavior that can help predict their likelihood of churning. Regression analysis, decision trees, and machine learning algorithms are common methods for predicting churn [4]. Historical data such as customer demographics, subscription information, usage patterns, and customer interactions are collected and analyzed. This data is then used to train the churn prediction models [5]. These models consider different variables such as customer age, subscription type, frequency of usage, and satisfaction levels to identify patterns that indicate a customer may be at risk of churning [6]. Once the churn models are trained, they are applied to new data to predict the likelihood of a customer churning [7]. These predictions can then be used by businesses to identify customers who are at a higher risk of churning and take proactive measures to prevent it. Predicting customer churn in subscription-based businesses refers to identifying customers likely to end their subscriptions with a company and finding ways to keep them [8]. This is a crucial issue for subscription-based businesses, directly impacting their revenue and growth. One of the main issues in predicting customer churn is data availability and quality. Subscription-based businesses collect large volumes of customer data, such as demographics, purchase history, and usage behavior. This data is often fragmented and stored in different systems, making it difficult to analyze and derive insights [9]. The data may need to be completed or accurate, leading to incorrect predictions. Another challenge is identifying the right factors that contribute to customer churn. When analyzing customer behavior, subscription-based businesses must consider various factors, such as pricing, product features, customer service, and competition. Identifying which factors impact customer churn most requires thorough data analysis and the use of advanced algorithms, which can be a complex and time-consuming process [10]. The main contribution of the research has the following:

- Identification of important factors: The research contributes to understanding key factors that lead to customer churn in subscription-based businesses.
- Development of predictive models: The study presents various predictive models for customer churn and evaluates their effectiveness in terms of accuracy and precision.
- Impact on business and customer retention: By accurately predicting customer churn, subscription-based businesses can proactively retain customers and minimize revenue loss.

II. RELATED WORKS

Mayya, R., et al. [11] have discussed e-commerce; subscription models mean a pricing strategy where customers pay an ongoing fee to get access to products or services subscribed for during the period the user has purchased. E-commerce analytics uses this data to track and analyze consumer behavior, purchase trends, etc., which can help you make informed decisions and better business strategy forever. Zimal, S., et al. [12] have discussed the process of using algorithms and statistical models on customer data to predict the probability of future churn, which is called Customer Churn Prediction with Machine Learning. It allows businesses to predict and prevent customer churn, subsequently improving their retention rate and, thus, their performance. Jang, K., et al. [13] have discussed Churn prediction, which is the use of mathematical algorithms and analytical techniques to predict a point in some future time when players will likely stop playing. Game developers can leverage this state so that their free-to-play games retain more users and a larger player lifetime value. Analyzing player behavioral data to come up with identifying those patterns that may be an early warning sign of churn.

Gasi, I.,et,al.[14] have discussed that using machine learning models, digital subscription services could predict customer churn and use place-based efficient customer retention techniques. By pooling together volumes of data from different sources and applying sophisticated ML algorithms, companies can recognize the patterns and behaviors leading to churn. More importantly, they can make headway by preventing costly subscriber turnover and bolstering their top line. Ibrahim, A.,et al.[15] have discussed Machine learning-based Churn Analysis, a methodology focusing on churn-specific indicators and patterns in customer behavior using complex algorithms and statistical models. It helps organizations predict which customers are likely to churn, and they can take necessary actions proactively for better customer retention and satisfaction. Sur, S.,et,al.[16] have discussed a model created using a Deep Learning algorithm that analyses the customer data based on various attributes and finds out how possible they can be a churn, i.e., quitting/discontinuing with business from your company. In this model, companies can recognize hundreds of risks on the horizon for customers and deal with them in advance to save their base from further diminution by keeping hold of stratified levels of customer satisfaction. Belchior, L. M.,et,al.[17] have discussed Churn Prediction, which is the practice of identifying customers who are expected to cancel a subscription or stop using the service. To do so, it predicts customer behavior by implementing data analysis and machine learning techniques that enable companies to react proactively towards retaining customers and lifting subscription revenue. Lampinen, S.,et,al.[18] have discussed that leading to the top is customer engagement, which is important in any business's success. Its sales data is fed into models that predict when a customer will churn or upgrade, which allows firms to analyze their customer base for effective engagement and retention. Companies can enhance customer loyalty and increase revenue by targeting otherwise high-risk customers with personalized offers to upgrade. Vemulapalli, G.,et,al.[19] have discussed these predictive models, which use artificial intelligence to analyze customer data and behaviors and detect patterns indicative of a possible churn outcome. Using this technology, company's benefit the most by creating preemptive strategies to decrease churn, like personalized retention efforts and focused marketing campaigns, which can increase customer satisfaction and loyalty. Çelik, O.,et,al.[20] have discussed that customer churn analysis is a key component of anticipating and stopping customers from leaving. Techniques including machine learning, data mining, and customer segmentation were employed. These techniques enable the detection of drivers causing downturns, segmenting at-risk customers, and targeting strategies to improve customer retention.

III. PROPOSED MODEL

A model in machine learning when the training data was imbued with far too much contextual signal inevitably led to improved performance on test inference streams but a poor generalization. When the model is too powerful, overfitting happens when it starts learning noise and patterns related to training data. It might be an imbalanced dataset, with one class dominating in numbers.

$$MAE = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{b=1}^M |h_b - h|. \quad (1)$$

$$F(J/I) = \frac{F(J) * F(I/J)}{F(I)} \quad (2)$$

$$x_{\theta}(h) = \sigma(\theta^v h) \quad (3)$$

The problem with this approach is that you can have biased training and inaccurate predictions; the models will bet on one of its classes. The features driving the model's predictions may take much work to understand. It can make explaining the model's decisions all the more difficult, which might limit its usefulness for real-world tasks. A lot of missing data in a dataset can lead to trying to make predictions with bias or inaccuracy. Machine learning is a category of algorithm and model that seeks to learn from data without being explicitly programmed, providing various predictions or decisions. A machine learning model should bring novelty to the table. This means that the model should propose an altered method by which certain task or challenge can be tackled. It could mean adding new techniques, algorithms, or data sources to increase the accuracy and efficiency of that model.

$$\sigma(w) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-w}} \quad (4)$$

$$b(h) = 1 - f_1^2 - p_0^2 \quad (5)$$

$$W = \frac{\beta}{se(\beta)} \sim M(0,1) \quad (6)$$

The most powerful machine learning model is a new type of algorithm as well, and it would have the best insight into what part of that big data needs addressing and how. A technical novelty in a machine learning model is key to expanding what can be done and helps enable innovation across entire industries, including healthcare, finance, or technology.

3. 1. Construction

Developing a Machine Learning Model is a step-by-step process involving Data preparation, pre-processing, model selection, and training /evaluation. Getting the required data for the model includes dealing with missing data, handling outliers, or removing features because they are not informative.

Target Training Set: Machine Learning algorithms Training Target Set | Supervised Machine Learning Task It is typically the data you train a model or classifier on. In other words, it is the training data that we feed to an algorithm and use for prediction (it's kind of a black box) on new unseen observations.

Source Domain: The source domain is the data from which you have a target training set in machine learning. This source data can be anything from historical records, simulation models, or experimentally generated datasets. Fig 1 Shows the Construction Model.

Fig 1: Construction Model

Initial Feature Subset: The first type of feature subset is the target training set that consists of chosen features and selected variables from the source domain. Selecting an initial feature subset allows your algorithm to make accurate predictions and should be aimed at pinpointing the most powerful, useful features.

Combine: Ensemble Learning combines multiple machine learning models or algorithms to obtain higher accuracy in the prediction. Combining different models aims to reduce bias and variance and overcome overfitting in the ultimate classification.

The Conversion of data into a machine-readable format is called Data pre-processing. It involves data normalization, standardization, and feature selection. The next step is to select a model which will act depending on the problem and dataset. It means tuning the model with parameters that maximize its performance. This model is then validated on a new data part to measure how well it fares. This is accomplished via metrics such as accuracy, precision, and recall. The model might need extra tuning and more retraining if it fails to deliver performance. Deploy the model to production to be used for predicting new inconsistent data.

$$G = 1 - \max_k (p_{mk}) \tag{7}$$

$$E = \sum_{k=1}^Y f_{ny} (1 - f_{ny}) \tag{8}$$

This process may need to be revisited as more data points are collected or business dynamics change, necessitating changes in the model. Building a Machine Learning Model goes through iterative steps, from cleaning and formatting the data, selecting an appropriate algorithm for training, measuring its performance, and then deploying it in real-world production applications.

3. 2. Operating principle

Machine learning models are self-operating systems that can glean knowledge of pattern recognition using algorithms and statistical methods from data sources with or without explicit instructions on performing a given task. These models can train over time, and as more data comes in, that will enable such general learning.

Reading Data: In any ML project, the first step is data reading. This includes data from different sources, like a CSV file, database, or API. Data can be in many formats and shapes, so loading the data properly is very important to do any further analysis.

Decision Tree: A decision tree is a supervised learning algorithm that can be used for both regression and classification tasks. This builds a tree structure that represents the list of questions you asked and their answers. Fig 2 Shows the Operating Principle Model.

Fig 2: Operating Principle Model

Data Pre-processing: Data Pre-processing is an indispensable step in any machine learning project. This process includes cleaning, converting, and sub setting the data to be prepared for training.

LightGBM: Gradient Boosting Machine uses tree-based learning algorithms. It works on the principle of combining many weak learners to form a strong model. LightGBM builds decision trees sequentially so that the next tree reduces errors.

$$RSS + \lambda \sum_{a=1}^f \beta_a^2 \tag{9}$$

$$RSS + \lambda \sum_{a=1}^f |\beta_a| \tag{10}$$

The model is trained by fitting it to a dataset containing features and their corresponding labels, with the ultimate goal of minimizing error when predicting said label. It continues in a loop until the model attains an acceptable level of accuracy. And later, this trained model can predict new data values it has never seen. We pass the latest data to the model in prediction, generating an output depending on what it has learned from training.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Supervised, Unsupervised, and Semi-supervised are the various types of learning based on whether training data has a label or not. They can also apply different approaches like Regression, Classification, or Clustering based on the nature of the problems they are solving. An ML model learns from a training set to provide predictive or decision power based on patterns found in the data

4.1. Accuracy

The performance for which the machine learning model will be able to predict customer churn. Fig 3 shows the Computation of recall.

Fig 3: Computation of recall

We will assess this on how well our model predicts everything based on the percentage of right predictions.

4.2. Precision

The two main criteria for measuring a model's performance in binary classification, such as customer churn prediction, are precision and recall. Precision is the proportion of actual positives to predicted positives, while recall is the number of true positive observations. Fig 4 shows the Computation of accuracy.

Fig 4: Computation of accuracy

If you use classification for churn prediction, your model should have high precision and recall scores.

4.3. Specificity

A confusion matrix is simply a table that summarizes the performance of our machine learning model by giving us counts for true positives, false negatives, true negatives, and false positives. Fig 5 shows the Computation of specificity.

Fig 5: Computation of specificity

It is a handy guide to check the accuracy of your churn prediction model. AUC is one of the well-known metrics used to measure how well or bad a machine learning model does, especially in binary classification problems. Fig 6 shows the Computation of miss rate.

Fig 6: Computation of miss rate

It measures how well the model can predict data points with all possible threshold values. The higher the AUC, the better your model's performance of the model.

CONCLUSION

In subscription-based businesses, the ability of Machine Learning models to predict churn with high accuracy has been established. These models use historical data and algorithms to find churn-related patterns and trends objectively. It can also be consistently updated and refined as per transformation in customer behavior so that you do find goodness in them. However, the usefulness of these models is directly proportional to the availability of data with quality. Companies should periodically gather and analyze data to make sure their machine-learning models are accurate and reliable. Implementing Machine Learning techniques to predict customer churn can provide companies with the necessary information to take action before a customer reaches that point, allowing for efforts to retain customers and increase profits.

REFERENCES

- [1] Morozov, V., Mezentseva, O., Kolomiiets, A., & Proskurin, M. (2022). Predicting customer churn using machine learning in IT startups. In *Lecture Notes in Computational Intelligence and Decision Making: 2021 International Scientific Conference "Intellectual Systems of Decision-making and Problems of Computational Intelligence"*, Proceedings (pp. 645-664). Springer International Publishing.
- [2] Agarwal, V., Taware, S., Yadav, S. A., Gangodkar, D., Rao, A. L. N., & Srivastav, V. K. (2022, October). Customer-Churn Prediction Using Machine Learning. In *2022 2nd International Conference on Technological Advancements in Computational Sciences (ICTACS)* (pp. 893-899). IEEE.
- [3] Deligiannis, A., & Argyriou, C. (2020). Designing a real-time data-driven customer churn risk indicator for subscription commerce. *International Journal of Information Engineering and Electronic Business*, 11(4), 1.
- [4] Aljifri, A. (2024). Predicting Customer Churn in a Subscription-Based E-Commerce Platform Using Machine Learning Techniques.
- [5] Flöjls, A., & Hägg, A. (2020). Churn Prediction: Predicting User Churn for a Subscription-based Service using Statistical Analysis and Machine Learning Models.
- [6] Zhang, S., Jiang, P., Moghtaderi, A., & Liss, A. (2021). Deep Ensemble Learning for Early-Stage Churn Management in Subscription-Based Business. In *Advances in Data Science and Information Engineering: Proceedings from ICDATA 2020 and IKE 2020* (pp. 283-298). Springer International Publishing.
- [7] Peddarapu, R. K., Ameena, S., Yashaswini, S., Shreshta, N., & PurnaSahithi, M. (2022, December). Customer Churn Prediction using Machine Learning. In *2022 6th International Conference on Electronics, Communication and Aerospace Technology* (pp. 1035-1040). IEEE.
- [8] Barr, K., & Pettersson, H. (2019). Predicting and Explaining Customer Churn for an Audio/e-book Subscription Service using Statistical Analysis and Machine Learning.
- [9] Shah, M., Adiga, D., Bhat, S., & Vyeth, V. (2019). Prediction and causality analysis of churn using deep learning. *Comput Sci Inf Technol*, 9(13), 153-165.
- [10] Prabadevi, B., Shalini, R., & Kavitha, B. R. (2023). Customer churning analysis using machine learning algorithms. *International Journal of Intelligent Networks*, 4, 145-154.
- [11] Mayya, R., Puranik, P., Balar, R., & Rahman, S. (2021). Subscription Models and Analytics in E-Commerce. *Grenze International Journal of Engineering & Technology (GIJET)*, 7(1).
- [12] Zimal, S., Shah, C., Borhude, S., Birajdar, A., & Patil, S. (2023). Customer churn prediction using machine learning. *Int J Res Appl Sci Eng Technol (IJRASET)*.
- [13] Jang, K., Kim, J., & Yu, B. (2021, April). On analyzing churn prediction in mobile games. In *Proceedings of the 2021 6th International Conference on Machine Learning Technologies* (pp. 20-25).
- [14] Gasi, I., & Linderoth, P. (2024). Combining ML Models for Churn Prediction and Customer Retention Strategies within Digital Subscription Services.
- [15] Ibrahim, A., (2024). Machine Learning-Powered Churn Analysis: Identifying Key Indicators and Predictive Patterns in Customer Behavior.
- [16] Sur, S., Sil, R., Bhushan, B., Bhattacharya, P., & Kumar, A. (2023, September). Customer Churn Prediction Model Using Deep Learning. In *International Conference on Intelligence Science* (pp. 297-308). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore.
- [17] Belchior, L. M., (2022). Churn Prediction in Online Newspaper Subscriptions (Master's thesis, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa (Portugal)).
- [18] Lampinen, S., & Salmela, D. S. T. L. (2022). Modeling Customer Engagement with churn and upgrade prediction (Doctoral dissertation, Master's thesis, University of Helsinki).
- [19] Vemulapalli, G., (2024). AI-Driven Predictive Models Strategies to Reduce Customer Churn. *International Numeric Journal of Machine Learning and Robots*, 8(8), 1-13.

- [20] Çelik, O., & Osmanoglu, U. O. (2019). Comparing to techniques used in customer churn analysis. Journal of Multidisciplinary Developments, 4(1), 30-38.

Theses:

- [21] D.S. Chan, Theory and implementation of multidimensional discrete systems for signal processing, doctoral diss., Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge, MA, 1978. (12)

Proceedings Papers:

- [22] W.J. Book, Modelling design and control of flexible manipulator arms: A tutorial review, Proc. 29th IEEE Conf. on Decision and Control, San Francisco, CA, 1990, 500-506 (12)

Citation: Anusha Musunuri. (2024). Machine Learning Model for Predicting Customer Churn in Subscription Based Business. International Journal of Artificial Intelligence & Machine Learning, 3(2), 211–220

Article Link:

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJAIML/VOLUME_3_ISSUE_2/IJAIML_03_02_017.pdf

Abstract:

https://iaeme.com/Home/article_id/IJAIML_03_02_017

Copyright: © 2024 Authors. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

This work is licensed under a **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0)**.

✉ editor@iaeme.com